

FINAL CONFERENCE REPORT

EUYD10 EU YOUTH CONFERENCE IN BUDAPEST, HUNGARY

7 -10 SEPTEMBER, 2024

Title: **EUJD10 EU Youth Conference in Budapest, Hungary. Final Conference Report**

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The EU Youth Conference (EUYC) took place in Budapest, Hungary, between 8th and 10th September 2024 under the Hungarian Presidency of the Council of the EU and brought together 159 participants. The thematic framework of the 10th Cycle of the EU Youth Dialogue (EUJD10) was defined by Youth Goal no.3 “Enable and ensure the inclusion of all young people in society” and summarised under the title “WE NEED YOUTH”. The EUJD10 Budapest was the third conference under the Trio Presidency Spain-Belgium-Hungary. This report summarises the conference deliberations and provides verbatim outcomes of the work of the conference participants, as well as detailed information on conference proceedings, and delivered inputs.

Participants of the EUJD10 Budapest worked towards delivering input on two key topics: rural youth, and future of the EU Youth Dialogue. The future of the EU Youth Dialogue was explored via SWOT analysis performed by the EUJD10 Budapest participants during one of the working group sessions. In case of the rural youth, the following subthemes were tackled:

- Education, talent development and training opportunities
- Employment and skill development opportunities
- Social support system and welfare policies
- Access to essential infrastructure
- Active participation in policy discussions
- Mental and physical health
- Entrepreneurship, farmership and employment opportunities
- Climate change and energy scarcity
- Demographic challenges and aging of local communities
- Access to national and EU instruments

All of these topics were tackled in working groups supported by facilitators in terms of work dynamics, and by harvesters in terms of capturing the outcomes of the deliberations. Working groups were also supported by policymakers during one of the sessions. Editing team consisting of representatives of the Hungarian National Youth Council, the European Youth Forum, the Hungarian Presidency team, and researchers supporting the EUJD10, subsequently summarised the outcomes of the working groups into draft texts suitable for policy documents prepared by the Hungarian Presidency of the Council of the EU. The summarised draft policy texts are included verbatim in this report, and the outcomes of the working group deliberations are quoted in an annex to this report as well.

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INTRODUCTION

The EU Youth Conference (EUYC) took place in Budapest, Hungary, between 8th and 10th September 2024 under the Hungarian Presidency of the Council of the EU, and brought together 159 participants: 84 national youth delegates, 55 ministerial delegates and 20 INGYO delegates. The thematic framework of the 10th Cycle of the EU Youth Dialogue (EUJD10) was defined by Youth Goal no.3 “Enable and ensure the inclusion of all young people in society” and summarised under the title “WE NEED YOUTH”. The EUYC Budapest was the third conference under the Trio Presidency Spain-Belgium-Hungary, and it had the following main aims:

- To ensure that policy recommendations are created from the findings of the EUJD and from the consultation and implementation phases of the 10th cycle.
- To find solutions on local, regional, national and European level that facilitate access to information and possibilities for young people living in rural and remote areas, especially those with fewer opportunities, to create chances for them and make use of their untapped potential to prosper locally.

Additional objectives were also set for the EUYC Budapest, namely:

- The Hungarian Presidency places a particular emphasis on its role as 'honest broker', aiming to mediate independently between the positions and expectations of the participants in line with the theme and objectives of the conference.
- The trio of Spain, Belgium, and Hungary (ES-BE-HU) want to ensure that their EUJDs and other presidency events are as sustainable, safe, inclusive and accessible as possible.
- The Hungarian Presidency seek to foster meaningful discussions among young people, youth organisations, policymakers, and political decision-makers within the European Union. The goal is to address important issues for young people and explore possible ways to enhance their lives in Europe.

These aims were achieved through deliberations in working groups in which participants of the EUYC Budapest contributed to the topic of rural youth and the topic of the future of the EU Youth Dialogue. In both cases, working group participants deliberated and created ideas which were subsequently summarised by the Editing Team and included in the Council documents of the Hungarian Presidency.

The editing team was supporting the EUYC Budapest participants in creating the final inputs for the policy documents, collecting ideas via the team of harvesters, and summarising these ideas in a language fit for policy documents. The participants of the EUYC Budapest were supported by a web-based application enabling communication and document sharing.

This report summarises the key discussions from the EUYC Budapest, and it also provides verbatim outcomes of the working group efforts, as well as the full conference programme in the annex.

DIVERSITY SURVEY

The EUYC Budapest participants were offered a chance to participate in a diversity survey where several questions concerning the background of the various delegates were asked. In total, 135 participants took part in the survey (in comparison with 106 at the EUYC Alicante and 144 at the EUYC Ghent), constituting a response rate of 84.9%. It is important to keep this response rate in mind as it clearly shows that not all of the EUYC Budapest participants took up the opportunity to fill in the diversity survey and all results only refer to those who kindly did.

Only a small minority of survey respondents was aged 16-18 (7%; in comparison with 7% at the EUYC Alicante and 4% at the EUYC Ghent), while most respondents were aged 19-25 (49%; in comparison to 41% at the EUYCs in Alicante and Ghent) and over 30 (22%; in comparison to 31% at the EUYC Alicante and 33% at the EUYC Ghent), with a rather large group of respondents aged 26-30 (21%; in comparison to 22% at the EUYC Alicante and 21% at the EUYC Ghent). Most of the survey respondents were female (53%; in comparison to 58% at the EUYC Alicante and 54% at the EUYC Ghent) with about 3% of those who identified as other gender or preferred not to answer (in comparison with 1% at the EUYC Ghent).

35% of the survey respondents claim to have been victims of hate speech at some point in their lives (in comparison with 31% at the EUYCs Alicante and Ghent) and 39% of them claim to have been victims of discrimination at some point in their lives (the same as at the EUYC Ghent, and less than at the EUYC Alicante where this has been claimed by 44% of respondents). When it comes to belonging to various minorities, survey respondents claimed to belong to the following ones:

- Ethnic minority: 13% (in comparison to 11% the EUYCs Alicante and Ghent)
- Religious minority: 11% (in comparison to 5% at the EUYC Alicante and 8% at the EUYC Ghent)
- LGBT minority: 21% (in comparison to 19% at the EUYC Alicante and 17% at the EUYC Ghent)
- Linguistic minority: 9% (in comparison to 7% at the EUYC Alicante, and the same as at the EUYC Ghent)
- Living with a disability: 4% (in comparison to 6% at the EUYC Alicante and 3% at the EUYC Ghent)
- Living with long-term health conditions: 13% (in comparison to 18% at the EUYC Alicante and 12% at the EUYC Ghent)
- Living in a rural or remote area: 22% (in comparison to 19% at the EUYC Alicante and 20% at the EUYC Ghent)

None of the survey respondents fell into the category of young people not in employment, education, or training (NEETs; in comparison to 3% at the EUYC Alicante and 1% at the EUYC Ghent), with 60% of respondents working full time (in comparison to 57% at the EUYC Alicante and 62% at the EUYC Ghent), 24% working part time (in comparison to 28% at the EUYC Alicante and 22% at the EUYC Ghent), and 52% being in full time education (in comparison with 37% at the EUYCs Alicante and Ghent). More than half of the survey respondents claimed to come from families with university backgrounds (56%, in comparison to 54% at the EUYC Alicante and 57% at the EUYC Ghent), while 6% of the survey participants were deeply worried about financial matters in their everyday lives (in comparison to 17% at the EUYC Alicante and 11% at the EUYC Ghent). Lastly, 24% of respondents claimed to have been newcomers to the EUYD processes, with the EUYC Budapest being their first ever activity within the EUYD context (in comparison to 41% at the EUYC Alicante and 31% at the EUYC Ghent).

It is apparent that the participant profiles of the EUYC Budapest were in many aspects similar to those of the EUYC Alicante and EUYC Ghent, suggesting a potentially similar levels of participant diversity at the EUYCs.

OFFICIAL OPENING

The EUYC Budapest started with an informal evening on Saturday 7th September 2024. **Ms. Zsófia Nagy-Vargha**, Deputy Secretary of State for Youth, welcomed all participants and thanked the team that prepared the EUYC Budapest. She noted that the EUYC Budapest is a continuation of the overall process linked to the Spanish and Belgian Presidency partners, and voiced hope for the EUYC Budapest to bring up new ideas.

The official opening of the EUYC Budapest was kicked off by the main facilitators, **Mr. Spyros Papadatos and Mrs. Enikő Gosztom**. They welcomed the participants and introduced the two main topics of the EUYD Budapest: rural youth and the future of the EUYD. They also outlined the conference proceedings, the online platform for information sharing during the EUYD Budapest, and welcomed the speakers. **Ms. Dorottya Budavári-Nagy**, the graphic facilitator, was introduced, and her work was shown to support the morning plenary.

Mr. Balázs Hankó, Minister of Culture and Innovation (Hungary), warmly welcomed participants in Hungary and at the EUYC Budapest, stressing that young people are the key to success of Europe and the EU, and therefore it is imperative to support them in reaching their dreams. Education, families, and labour market were mentioned as the vital areas in which young people need support. Competition at the labour market and in education is rising, with young people in rural areas lacking for opportunities available in larger settlements. Rural youth education, labour market integration and family opportunities should be supported by the EU and by the national governments. Universities in Hungary, for example, are developing schemes in which young people from rural areas are provided with mentoring and other tools to boost their engagement in tertiary education. Increased numbers of young people from disadvantaged backgrounds can therefore be seen across variety of educational institutions. This is a result of strengthening of partnerships among the vocational training sector, universities, and the labour market. Pannónia Scholarship Programme was set up in Hungary and offers learning mobilities similar to those offered by the Erasmus+ scheme. The Hungarian government offers family support via tax reductions for young people entering the labour market, and also in housing subsidies for young people based in rural areas.

Ms. Pia Ahrenkilde Hansen, Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture at the European Commission, stressed in her video message that the EU Youth Dialogue makes continuous progress towards inclusion and towards assisting the EU policymakers in creating new policies with and for the young people. Youth participation and welfare are high on the EU policy agendas, underlining the need to create spaces for meeting of policymakers and young people. Various bodies will be set up towards that goal, the Erasmus+ programme will be strengthened, and the EUYD future is to be debated during the EUYC Budapest in order to assist with the development of the EUYD for the upcoming seven years.

Ms. Laure Verstraete, Board Member of the European Youth Forum, underlined that the EU Youth Conferences are valuable not only for the impact on the young people Europe-wide, but also for the informal networking opportunities. Both of those aspects offer space for deliberations and seeking of solutions for problems young people feel need tackling. She also stressed that the 10th cycle of the EUYD is a perfect moment for deliberating on the future of the EUYD as such. She highlighted that these places in which young people create ideas which are subsequently taken on board by policymakers are crucial for democracy and for all young people in Europe. Rural youth still face difficulties on many levels, and it is crucial to tackle these inequalities and make sure that those young people and any other groups, such as the LGBTQI+ young people, are included, respected, and welcomed. Erasmus+ and the European Solidarity Corps programmes are valuable tools to tackle inequalities, and the EUYD is a unique space for inclusion of young people in the democratic processes. Consultations happening during the EUYD and assisted by the National Youth Councils and the National Working Groups are key to keep this deliberation process running smoothly. A moment of silence for the young people dying in armed conflicts around the world was held.

Mr. Péter Kovács, President of the National Youth Council of Hungary, welcomed all participants and stressed that youth is the key to sorting out the largest challenges the world is facing. The EUYC Budapest is offering space to co-shape future of the world, it creates opportunities for creating new connections, and hopefully also builds basis for success of young people in the future: peaceful and inclusive Europe. Schengen area and the EU build freedoms of travel, connecting, meeting, but they should not be taken for granted. Wars raging at this time in different places across the world remind us that constant effort is needed to keep democracies running. Division and isolation of the past century is still vividly remembered, and

young people should not be victims of political battles, and they should be able to enjoy the mobility opportunities that the Erasmus+ programme offers. Sustainability is driven by ideas of young people, and they should be listened to and encouraged to take action. Collaboration and dialogue as well as shared responsibility are keys to success, and that is what the EUYC Budapest offers: to work on pressing matters of today. Mr. Kovács thanked the team of young people who have contributed to organising the EUYC Budapest.

Mr. Dan Moxon and Mr. Ondřej Bárta, the European researchers working with the 10th Cycle of the EUYD were invited to the stage to summarise the developments of the EUYD10, to outline the role of the EUYC Budapest in the overall cycle, and to explain the collaboration between the working groups and the editing team. Mr. Moxon summarised that the whole EUYD10 revolved around the European Youth Goal no.3: Inclusive Societies. Already at the EUYC Alicante under the Spanish Presidency of the Council of the EU, a conversation was kicked off about how we can create a more inclusive Europe for young people and especially those who are often marginalised, excluded or have fewer opportunities than others such as rural youth. He also underlined the role of the national consultations on the topic of inclusion in which about 30,000 young people from all walks of life took part in late 2023 and early 2024. He outlined that the results of these extensive consultation efforts created a basis for deliberations at the EUYC Ghent under the Belgian Presidency of the Council of the EU, resulting in 6 recommendations and more than 30 implementation actions included in the follow-up policy documents. All of these outcomes subsequently created grounds for implementation phase of the EUYD10, as can be seen in the implementation report available to the EUYC Budapest participants. Mr. Bárta further elaborated on the role of the EUYC Budapest in seeking answers to challenges faced by young people in rural areas. He also stressed that the EUYC Budapest participants will be able to provide their insights into the potential future developments of the EUYD. All of these deliberations will take place in working group setups supported by teams of facilitators and harvesters. In order to ensure that deliberations stay focused on the content and do not get slowed down by looking for the right wording and format, the editing team was set up. The editing team will work with the inputs provided by the working groups and summarise and transform them into a text suitable for the policy documents by the Hungarian Presidency of the Council of the EU. In order to keep the process open, transparency rules were created and were presented to the EUYC Budapest participants. The editing team will stay true to the ideas created in the working groups, it will ensure the text is suitable for the policy documents, and it will come back to the working groups in case clarifications are needed. Members of the editing team were also introduced: a representative of the European Youth Forum, a representative of the Hungarian National Youth Council, a representative of the Hungarian Presidency team, and both of the European researchers supporting the EUYD10.

Mr. Spyros Papadatos and Mrs. Enikő Gosztom further introduced the overall programme of the EUYC Budapest, including all practicalities, the evening programmes, and the milestones. Topics of working groups were also introduced, and participants were kindly asked to start their working group deliberations.

WORKSHOP ON THE FUTURE OF THE EU YOUTH PROGRAMMES

The Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture (DG EAC, European Commission) hosted a consultation on the next generation of the EU Youth Programmes. The purpose of the session was to get input and ideas from youth delegates on the next generation and further development of the EU youth programmes, which is currently being negotiated with the EU Member States. The discussion focused on six themes: inclusion and accessibility,

bringing together different generations, digital transformation, environment and climate, community engagement, and mental health and well-being. The results of the consultation will be published on the European Youth Portal.

WORKING GROUP SESSIONS

During Sunday 8th of September 2024, and Monday 9th of September 2024, six working groups in the total length of 8 hours and 30 minutes, featuring also a session with policymakers in the length of 1.5 hours (please see Annex 4 for the list of policymakers), allowed EUYC Budapest participants to deliberate on ten key topics related to the overarching theme “rural youth” as follows (please see Annex 2 for their detailed descriptions):

- **Education, talent development and training opportunities**
- **Employment and skill development opportunities**
- **Social support system and welfare policies**
- **Access to essential infrastructure**
- **Active participation in policy discussions**
- **Mental and physical health**
- **Entrepreneurship, farmership and employment opportunities**
- **Climate change and energy scarcity**
- **Demographic challenges and aging of local communities**
- **Access to national and EU instruments**

A separate working group session focusing on the future of the EU Youth Dialogue was also held in the total length of 2 hours on Monday 9th of September 2024. This session was the same for all ten working groups, so all EUYC Budapest participants had a chance to voice their opinions on this topic.

The working groups were supported by teams consisting of facilitators and harvesters. While the facilitators were focusing on the group and deliberation dynamics and workflow, the harvesters were collecting ideas and supporting the process of drafting concrete implementing measures.

The session with policymakers during which the participants had an opportunity to refine their work based on further deliberations brought many interesting insights. Participants were urged to take into account the intra-state mobilities across different rural areas, to consider remote work as an opportunity for rural areas, and to look at cooperation between centralised and decentralised state bodies and other actors in rural areas. Participants were also cautioned that not all measures are realistically implementable in all countries, especially when it comes to tax relief strategies. Policymakers also stressed the vital importance of needs assessments, cost-benefit analysis, and local surveys before any measures are implemented in rural areas, and also the potential to joining initiatives which already exist in these areas (or applying instruments existing at other levels). It is necessary to consider not only the cost of establishing new initiatives, but also the cost of their maintenance. It is equally important to ensure that the support for rural areas is reaching its target group, and not creating a new service sector, as it can be happening in digitalisation of the farming sector.

WORLD CAFÉ

A World Café session where policymakers met with EUYC Budapest participants was held on 10th September 2024 and lasted for an hour. The three main goals of the session were as follows:

- to create a safe environment in which everyone feels comfortable asking questions and sharing ideas about youth policy,
- to provide opportunities for young people to ask questions and learn about the various approaches and policies in different EU Member States, and
- to exchange ideas and knowledge about the diverse national practices in the field of youth policy.

Tables were prepared where informal conversations took place between policymakers and the EUYC Budapest participants. Each of the tables were occupied by a Director General for Youth from a given EU Member State, while young people visited different tables to learn about youth policies in various contexts. In order to facilitate the debates, guiding questions were prepared:

- Support for young people from rural areas with fewer opportunities on the basis of the European Youth Strategy:
 - Based on the EU Youth Strategy pillars, what fields where the policy decision makers can help and support the disadvantaged young people and young people who are living in rural areas?
 - How do you see the future of EU youth programmes? How do you see the programmes evolving to better meet the needs of young people from rural and disadvantaged areas?
 - What are the best practices to inform young people from rural areas and disadvantaged young people about the EU Youth Dialogue and to involve them effectively in the process?
- Support for young people in rural areas and in disadvantaged regions at the national level:
 - What support measures and incentives are available to help disadvantaged young people or young people living in rural and areas to prosper locally
 - What national programs, good practices and forums exist in your country that effectively involve young people in decision-making?
 - What approaches and good practices are used to ensure that information about the opportunities offered by European Union or national programs is more effectively disseminated to young people with fewer opportunities or young people from rural areas?

During the debates, digitalisation in education was critically explored, with some tendencies to retreat back to printed materials in order to benefit students and pupils in Finland. Fears of climate change impacts and of possible war engagements concerning EU Member States were mentioned as important to young people in rural areas and beyond. It was also underlined that rural youth should be one of the priorities at the EU level, enabling them to access mobility opportunities, such as those offered by the Erasmus+ programme. Voting at 16 was also discussed, with young people underlining the imbalance among the EU Member States created by the fact that in some countries young people can vote as of the age of 16, while in others as of 18. The importance of local languages to young people in rural areas and beyond

was also a topic of debates. Irish, Breton, and other languages seem to be popular among young people, and this has consequences for informal activities, such as sports.

PLENARY CONCLUSIONS

The EUYC Budapest facilitators, **Mr. Spyros Papadatos** and **Mrs. Enikő Gosztom**, summarised the proceedings of the whole conference and invited the editing team to present the outcomes. The editing team consisted of the representative of the Hungarian National Youth Council **Mrs. Réka Gaján**, the representative of the European Youth Forum **Mrs. Laure Verstraete**, the representative of the Hungarian Presidency of the Council of the EU **Mrs. Dorottya Kósa**, and the researchers supporting the 10th cycle of the EU Youth Dialogue, **Mr. Ondřej Bárta** and **Mr. Dan Moxon**.

The editing team members described the process of creating the presented outcomes. Firstly, the ideas were proposed by the participants within the working group settings, supported by the seasoned facilitators. Subsequently, these ideas were captured by the harvesters present in the working groups and passed on to the editing team. The editing team eventually summarised these ideas and created draft texts suitable for the policy documents prepared by the Hungarian Presidency of the Council of the EU. These draft texts concerned both the topic of rural youth and the topic of the future of the EU Youth Dialogue. The draft text concerning rural youth was presented as follows:

“Young people during the Hungarian EU Youth Conference in September 2024, proposed to make rural and remote areas more vibrant and attractive for young people by:

- *Promoting meaningful rural youth participation, especially on issues related to environmental sustainability as well as mental and physical health*
- *Fostering supportive rural communities, challenging prejudice, building accessible intergenerational dialogue, and common spaces as well as strengthening visions for the future.*
- *Increasing access to infrastructure, tailored to the needs of young people, such as internet connectivity, information, transportation, clean energy, as well as physical and mental health services.*
- *Raising awareness of alternative employment pathways such as remote working and innovative farming.*

EU, national and local instruments should fit the needs, realities, capacities and resources of young people from rural and remote areas and:

- *Provide support for youth participation within rural development and decision making for example through youth ambassadors, advisory boards, local youth councils and participatory budgeting.*
- *Support rural entrepreneurship including farming through awareness-raising on existing EU and national programmes, mentorship, promotion of digital transformation and fostering the use of financial incentives such as tax relief or co-funding opportunities.*
- *Promote youth-friendly platforms for accessing information on youth programmes, quality employment opportunities and funding as well as launching an EU-wide campaign to foster equal access to work.*
- *Encourage quality learning opportunities and youth initiatives that widen the experiences of rural youth, such as urban-rural youth exchanges, climate projects,*

mobile and outreach youth workers, as well as engagement in rural youth organisations.

- *Improving access to services and information related to mental health through inspiring local action and fostering dialogue on existing funding opportunities and facilities.”*

The final notes on the future of the EU Youth Dialogue were presented as well:

“Strengths of EUYD

- *Gathers young people's input for shaping policies and raises awareness of the needs of young people*
- *Strengthens advocacy for youth organisations*
- *Fosters dialogue between young people and decision makers and ensures real representation and visibility of youth voices*
- *Creates space for inclusion, diversity and interculturality in youth participation*
- *Is a large and an institutionally well-established process, including stable funding*
- *Can have an impact on policy and decision making at all levels*

Weaknesses of EUYD

- *Perceived as lacking in diversity and inclusion of the marginalised groups*
- *Participation of decision-makers and representatives of the EU institutions can be limited*
- *Lacks sufficient dissemination, visibility, and promotion - Is not well known among young people*
- *Lacks transparency, accountability and follow*
- *Lack of preparation of young delegates for participation in the EU Youth Conferences*
- *Challenging implementation results at all levels due to short timeframes and lack of accountability*
- *Lacks monitoring, evaluation, and impact assessment on all levels*

Threats for developing EUYD

- *Democratic backsliding and threats to democratic environment and culture at large*
- *Low participation rates, under or overrepresentation of certain groups of young people, organisations, etc.*
- *Lack of trust and interest (in results, in the process, by youth, by policymakers...)*
- *Threats of tokenism and youthwashing*

Opportunities for developing EUYD

- *Common standards for all delegates onboarding and selection processes*
- *Develop an impact report to monitor influence implemented.*
- *Creating a space for commenting on on-going EU work/policies*
- *Making reports, data and recommendations of the effectiveness of the EUYD available, and mainstream the impact of the dialogue*
- *Opportunities to involve more young people with disabilities, fewer opportunities as well as people from underrepresented regions*
- *The EUYD process should be operating on a higher political level, influence and prestige.”*

The EUYC Budapest participants were also informed that these were draft texts, and they can still be modified in the process of adoption of the policy documents.

Mr. Rareş Voicu, President of the European Youth Forum, stressed the moments of connections that happened during the EUYC Budapest. He also underlined that the solutions identified at the EUYC Budapest need to be meaningfully implemented in policymaking, with poverty and social exclusion being the key problem in the rural areas. Young people in rural areas are facing multiple obstacles, making it hard to be able to plan for the future, and adding to the risk of marginalisation of certain groups of young people. Discrimination is still present across the EU, for example with members of the LGBT community being pushed out of the public spaces. Opposing the influence of autocracies, which do not respect human rights, such as the Russian one, is essential to ensure that human rights are observed, to ensure that kindness and compassion stay at the core of our everyday lives. In case of rural areas, revitalisation is key, building up better infrastructure, innovative labour market solutions, and services tailored to the needs of the rural youth. This will enable young people to access opportunities, to enjoy youth work, and to be included and engaged. The European Youth Forum is committed to supporting youth-led EUYD processes, and to ensuring that the National Youth Councils are in the driving seats of the EUYD. He thanked the current cycle for supporting young people in having their voices heard. He thanked the team of the Hungarian Presidency of the Council of the EU for implementing a fantastic EUYC Budapest. A moment of silence for the young lives lost in senseless and cruel war of Russia against Ukraine was observed. He also stressed that the work of the youth delegates is especially relevant today, as it spreads hope young people need nowadays more than ever.

Mrs. Sophia Eriksson Waterschoot, Director for Youth, Education and Erasmus+ (DG EAC), at the European Commission, thanked the facilitators and the organising team, and appreciated the overall level of energy at the EUYC Budapest as well as its outcomes. She also thanked the Hungarian Presidency of the Council of the EU and the editing team for their work, and she appreciated insights concerning the rural youth included in the EUYC Budapest outcomes. She further stressed that the EU is currently in the process of establishing priorities and representatives of various offices after the latest EU elections. The President of the European Commission has been placing strong emphasis on young people, such as introducing a guiding principle of avoiding harm to future generations in all decisions and stressing the youth voices as key for shaping the future. Among other measures aimed at supporting young people, Youth Advisory Board will be established, an institute of the EU Commissioner for Intergenerational Fairness will be introduced, the Erasmus+ programme will be strengthened to enable more young people to participate, all of the EU Commissioners will be holding youth policy dialogues, and overall mainstreaming will be at the heart of the current European Commission actions. Mental health and digital sphere are also among the upcoming key priorities, including an action plan against cyber bullying, for example. The next Multiannual Financial Framework needs to be established, and the update of the EU Youth Strategy is also going to happen in coming years. Mrs. Waterschoot also acknowledged the learning experience of young people within the EUYD and underlined that it is crucial for links between the ongoing policy processes and the EUYD processes to be strengthened in the future. The EU Youth Check is a tool which the European Commission has committed to, and the potential of linking it with the EUYD should be explored. She concluded by thanking to all previous Presidencies for all their work.

Mrs. Veronika Varga-Bajusz, Hungarian State Secretary for Higher Education, Vocational and Adult Education and Youth Affairs, opened by stressing the need to avoid propaganda. She highlighted that Hungarian students were excluded from the Erasmus+ programme in a discriminatory manner and emphasised that Hungary was as democratic as the other EU states. The State Secretary went on to praise the EUYC Budapest, including both participants and organisers. She highlighted the value of the insights and practices in the field of youth coming from the event. She noted that by supporting young people we can work for a better

future in Europe. The State Secretary expressed that the Hungarian National Youth Council and other youth structures played an important role in Hungary. By engaging in regular dialogue with decision makers they helped Hungary develop policies that meet the needs of young people and to bridge the gap between youth and decision makers. She further highlighted that the EUYD was an essential part of this dialogue, as it allowed both sides to understand each other's perspectives. The State Secretary closed by noting that one size fits all solutions do not always work, so we require tailored support that fits the specific needs of young people in rural areas. Every young person deserves access to resources which ensure their success, and it is our shared mission to deliver it.

ANNEX 1: PROGRAMME OF THE EUYC BUDAPEST

Day 1: 7th September 2024

9:00 - 19:00 Arrivals, registration and hotel check-in for participants

15:00 - 17:00 Geocaching (optional) starts from Bálna Conference Centre

19:00 - 21:00 Informal opening dinner

Day 2: 8th September 2024

8:00 – 9:00 Participants arrive at the site of the Conference

9:00 – 10:30 Opening Plenary

- Balázs Hankó, Minister of Culture and Innovation of Hungary
- video from Pia Ahrenkilde Hansen, European Commission's Director-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture
- Laure Verstraete, European Youth Forum board member
- Péter Kovács, President of the National Youth Council
- Ondrej Barta and Dan Moxon, European researchers of the 10th Cycle

10:30 - 11:00 Coffee break

11:00 – 12:30 Working group session

12:30 - 13:30 Lunch

13:30 - 15:00 Working group session

15:00 - 15:30 Coffee break

15:30 –17:00 Working group session

18:00 – 20:00 Dinner

20:30 - Cultural program (organised by the Hungarian National Youth Council)

Day 3: 9th September 2024

8:00 – 9:00 Participants arrive at the site of the Conference

9:00 – 10:30 Working group session

10:30 – 11:00 Coffee break

11:00 – 12:00 Working group session

12:00 – 13:00 Lunch

13:00 – 14:30 Discussions with decision-makers in the framework of working group sessions

14:30 – 15:00 Coffee break

15:00 – 17:00 Working group session

17:00 – 18:00 Workshop by the European Commission: „The future generation of EU youth programmes” (optional)

19:00 – 21:00 Grand Gala Dinner in Europa Event Center

Day 4: 10th September 2024

8:00 – 9:00 Participants arrive at the site of the Conference

9:00 – 10:00 World Café, discussion between delegates and Director-Generals for Youth

10:00 – 10:30 Coffee break

10:30 – 12:00 Closing Plenary

- Veronika Varga-Bajusz, Hungarian State Secretary for Higher Education, Vocational and Adult Education and Youth Affairs
- Sophia Eriksson Waterschoot, European Commission’s Director for Youth, Education and Erasmus+
- Rareş Voicu, President of the European Youth Forum
- Péter Kovács, President of the Hungarian National Youth Council
- Réka Gaján, representative of the Hungarian National Youth Council
- Laure Verstraete, European Youth Forum board member
- Ondřej Bárta and Dan Moxon, European researchers of the 10th Cycle

12:00 – 13:00 Lunch

12:00 - Departure of EUYC participants

ANNEX 2: WORKING GROUP TOPICS

WG1. Education, talent development and training opportunities

(Enhancing and developing formal and non-formal education, talent development and training opportunities in rural areas)

Our Working Group will focus on finding solutions for rural youth for enhancing and developing education and training opportunities in rural areas, by addressing the interconnection between inequality and lack of access to education. We will explore the diversity of educational approaches, by clearly defining the roles of formal and non-formal education in cultivating better opportunities for rural youth. By identifying and promoting effective solutions for skills-building, talent development, and the necessary educational infrastructure, our Working Group aims to create educational pathways for rural youth to thrive! Our work and our solutions will contribute to bridging educational gaps and ensuring that rural communities are equipped with the resources and learning environment they need for sustainable growth.

WG2. Employment and skill development opportunities

(Fostering fair employment and applicable skill development opportunities for rural youth and improving their economic prospects)

Our Working Group will focus on coming up with solutions that enhance social inclusion and fair employment for young people from rural and remote areas across Europe. We will examine the unique challenges faced by rural communities, aiming to support the creation of equitable job opportunities that bridge the gap between urban and rural employment standards, access and opportunities. By fostering skill development tailored to the needs of rural areas, we seek to empower young people with the tools necessary for sustainable employment paths that will empower and revitalize rural areas. Our efforts will concentrate on mapping a supportive system that connects rural youth to emerging economic opportunities, ensuring that they can contribute meaningfully to their communities and beyond.

WG3. Social support system and welfare policies

(Improving and designing inclusive social support systems and welfare policies catering to the needs of rural youth)

Our Working Group will focus on improving and designing solutions in relation to inclusive social support systems and welfare policies tailored to the specific needs of rural youth in Europe. We will identify the existing gaps in social services and welfare policies, ensuring that rural youth have equal access to support systems that address their unique challenges. By mapping out tailored policies that prioritize inclusivity and equity, our Working Group aims to create a comprehensive framework that empowers rural youth to thrive! We will work towards developing comprehensive solutions that foster social well-being and ensure that no young person in rural areas is left behind.

WG4. Access to essential infrastructure

(Ensuring better access to essential infrastructure related to everyday life in rural and remote areas)

Our Working Group will focus on solutions ensuring better access to essential infrastructure that supports the everyday lives of young people in rural and remote areas. We will examine the current barriers to accessing vital services such as healthcare, education, physical and digital connectivity, which are crucial for the well-being, the participation and the development of rural youth. By proposing solutions for improvements and investments in infrastructure, our Working Group aims to bridge the gap between rural and urban areas, ensuring that young people in rural and remote regions have the necessary access to resources and opportunities like everyone else.

WG5. Active participation in policy discussions

(Achieving active participation of rural youth in policy discussions at local, regional, national and EU levels)

Our Working Group will focus on solutions that facilitate better the active participation of rural youth in policy discussions at local, regional, national, and EU levels. We will work on ways to empower young people from rural areas to have a voice in the decision-making processes that affect their lives, ensuring that their perspectives are represented and valued. From youth information to meaningful rural youth participation, we will look for solutions, tools and platforms, to bridge the participation gap and foster a culture of inclusivity and involvement in policy dialogues for young people from rural and remote areas. We are committed to ensuring that rural youth play a significant role in shaping policies that reflect their needs and aspirations, while also feeling ownership for such policies.

WG 6. Mental and physical health

(Improving mental and physical health of rural youth, especially those with fewer opportunities)

Our Working Group will focus on solutions around improving the mental and physical health of rural youth, with a particular emphasis on those with fewer opportunities. We will explore the unique health-related challenges faced by young people in rural areas, where access to healthcare services and wellness resources is often limited. By mapping ways for targeted support and initiatives that promote both mental and physical well-being, our Working Group aims to ensure that all rural youth have the opportunity to lead healthy lives. We will be developing solutions that address the specific needs of rural youth, fostering resilience and enhancing the overall quality of life.

WG7. Entrepreneurship, farmership and employment opportunities

(Development, diversification and proliferation of entrepreneurship, farmership and employment opportunities in rural areas.)

Our Working Group will focus on the development, diversification, and proliferation of entrepreneurship, farmership, and employment opportunities in rural areas. We will explore innovative solutions and strategies to revitalize local economies by supporting the growth of small businesses, agricultural initiatives, and new employment pathways tailored to the unique characteristics and strengths of rural communities. By putting entrepreneurship and enhancing job prospects in the centre, our Working Group aims to map solutions that empower rural youth

to create sustainable livelihoods, reduce economic disparities, and revitalize their communities, through building vibrant, self-sustaining rural economies that offer diverse opportunities for all.

WG8. Climate change and energy scarcity

(Revitalizing rural areas amidst climate change and energy scarcity)

Our Working Group will focus on solutions for revitalizing rural areas in the face of climate change and energy scarcity. We will explore sustainable ways to adapt rural communities to the growing environmental challenges while ensuring their resilience and long-term prosperity. From renewable energy sources to sustainable agricultural practices and climate-smart infrastructure, our Working Group aims to develop a framework that will empower rural areas to thrive in an increasingly uncertain future. We are committed to mapping solutions that not only mitigate the impacts of climate change, but also enhance the vitality and sustainability of rural communities for future generations as well.

WG9. Demographic challenges and aging of local communities

(Addressing the positive and negative effects of urbanisation, the aging of local communities and the demographic challenges of local areas)

Our Working Group will focus on addressing the positive and negative effects of urbanization, the aging of local communities, and the demographic challenges facing rural areas. We will explore the impact of population shifts on rural life, including the drain of young people to urban centres and the resulting demographic imbalances. By examining solutions to retain and attract young people in rural areas, support aging populations, and manage the challenges of urbanization, our Working Group aims to map sustainable solutions that balance growth and preserve the vitality of rural communities, in order for rural areas to remain vibrant, inclusive, and resilient in the face of demographic changes.

WG10. Access to national and EU instruments

(Enhancing access to national and EU instruments and initiatives at local level)

Our Working Group will focus on solutions which enhance access to national and EU instruments and initiatives for rural youth at the local level. We will work on ways to bridge the gap between rural communities and the resources available to them, addressing issues such as language barriers, by increasing awareness, understanding, and utilization of these tools. By identifying barriers to access and mapping solutions to overcome them, our Working Group focuses on the development and empowerment of rural youth to fully benefit from national and EU programs, so that they can thrive and contribute meaningfully to their communities.

ANNEX 3: OUTCOMES OF THE WORKING GROUP DELIBERATIONS: RURAL YOUTH

WG1. Education, talent development and training opportunities

What do the desired social change(s) in this theme look like?

- Exposure to representation of different minorities in educational materials and curriculum to decrease stereotypes that affect rural youth's choice of profession. Taking away obstacles which boost prejudice will make it possible for rural youth to reach their best potential.
- Access to more diverse opportunities, resources and information by raising awareness, making opportunities more accessible and increasing participation through outreach activities.

Implementing Measure no. 1

Title of the implementing measure

- Urban and rural school exchange program

Description of the implementing measure

- The mutual exchange program connects an urban and a rural school within national or European level, facilitating multiple short exchanges within a year. Students from both schools participate in exchanges, with urban students visiting rural areas and rural students experiencing city life. They stay with host families, engage in local activities, and explore cultural differences. Pupils are connected through a buddy program where they can connect informally.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- Social cohesion, information sharing, intercultural exchange

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- National, regional

Implementing Measure no. 2

Title of the implementing measure

- Targeted project funding for rural youth initiatives in EU programs

Description of the implementing measure

- In line with the EU diversity strategy, establish a dedicated funding stream for rural youth initiatives, supported by microgrants. These programs should focus on talent development, skill enhancement, and educational opportunities, incentivizing organizations to prioritize rural areas and increase youth engagement in EU initiatives.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- More ongoing and sustainable projects and more inclusion and participation.

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- EU

Implementing Measure no. 3

Title of the implementing measure

- Providing mobile youth work and information campaigns in rural areas

Description of the implementing measure

- Mobile youth workers visit a rural/remote area on a regular basis to host workshops based on the needs of local young people (e.g. career guidance, educational workshops, civic life participation.) They would also be providing information on local/regional/national/European/International opportunities for young people as well as assisting young people with finding or starting youth organizations in accordance with their interests.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- Improved inclusion, development of skills, raised awareness of opportunities through youth-friendly ways

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- Funding on a national level, implementation on a regional and local level

WG2. Employment and skill development opportunities

What do the desired social change(s) in this theme look like?

- Rural youth should have more easily access to well-funded and less bureaucratic programmes, whilst being correctly informed about such programmes along with other available employment opportunities.
- In rural areas, young people should benefit from equal chances of employment, regardless of their gender (expression), their sexual orientation or the specific community or minority they belong to.

Implementing Measure no. 1

Title of the implementing measure:

- An easily readable and user-friendly platform showing available opportunities

Description of the implementing measure:

- Create a user-friendly **platform** that centralises accessible information about youth programs, employment and skill development opportunities, along with available

fundings, using simple language. The Commission will be responsible for overseeing it and the member states are responsible for integrating and updating national opportunities. Involving youth councils, governments, NGOs/NGYOs, and stakeholders will help extend the reach of these opportunities and programmes, ensuring broader access for all rural youth, particularly those from diverse and underprivileged backgrounds.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful:

- Platform ensures accessible information to rural youth in simple language.

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- EU, National, and Regional Level

Implementing Measure no. 2

Title of the implementing measure

- Incentivising job relocation to rural areas and reform existing programs

Description of the implementing measure

- Reviewing and ensuring the efficiency and functionality of already existing EU and national programs, through a cooperation between NGOs, NGYOs, local structures, local government and the European Commission. The aim of more flexible programs is to incentivise companies to relocate job opportunities to rural areas in order to ensure a bigger variety and higher offer of employment possibilities and white collar jobs. Restructuring of the Youth Guarantee programme and Erasmus plus to better benefit the needs of young people living in rural areas.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- diverse job opportunities
- revitalise rural areas
- (prosperity)

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- From national and regional level targeting local communities and areas.
- Using EU programs.

Implementing Measure no. 3

Title of the implementing measure:

- EU-wide campaign fighting discrimination in the workplace

Description of the implementing measure

- A European-wide campaign against workplace discrimination towards minorities in their whole diversity (focusing on socioeconomic backgrounds, LGBTQIA+ individuals, religious and ethnic minorities, gender, and disabilities), particularly in rural youth. This campaign, monitored by European institutions and supported by national governments, will promote diversity and inclusivity in the workplace. Such regular monitoring will ensure accountability, with partnerships across sectors extending the campaign's reach and impact.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful:

- Public awareness initiatives, workshops, and policy recommendations will foster equal opportunities.

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- EU and National Level

WG3. Social support system and welfare policies

What do the desired social change(s) in this theme look like?

- Local public authorities establish mechanisms for facilitating the participation of young people in the decision making process.
- Revitalisation of rural areas by providing inclusive tools for young people to access education, employment, social welfare and guaranteeing basic infrastructure and facilities.

Implementing Measure no. 1

Title of the implementing measure

- European Strategy for Revitalising Rural Areas

Description of the implementing measure

- Create an EU strategy that sets guidelines to member states implementing national plans in developing proximity social support systems in the target areas: healthcare, education, social services and leisure. The European Commission with 1 delegate from the governments and 1 youth delegate from a rural area write the strategy in one year and member states have 10 years to implement. In the implementation phase it is strongly recommended to involve rural youth in the development of the measures.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- Provide a proximity system of social support and welfare that include all geographic areas

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- European / national

Implementing Measure no. 2

Title of the implementing measure

- Empowering youth self-employment with tax relief and financial support

Description of the implementing measure

- This proposal aims to promote youth self-employment through tax reliefs for young people and financial support (such as financial grants) for 1 to 3 years, tailored to regional professional needs. Additionally, young entrepreneurs living in or relocating to rural areas will receive co-funding for work infrastructure and be exempted from social security contributions.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- Fosters regional economic development, supports sustainable employment.

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- National / Local level

Implementing Measure no. 3

Title of the implementing measure

- Modernising Regional Industries Through Education and Entrepreneurial Support

Description of the implementing measure

- This proposal aims to enhance education through mentorship, training, and informal learning, focusing on modernising traditional farming and industries into innovative, entrepreneurial practices. Programs will provide accessible information on regional specifics, such as basic economics, infrastructure development, and access to support schemes.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- fostering innovation and sustainable growth, while supporting regional development.

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- European / National / Local level

WG4. Access to essential infrastructure

What do the desired social change(s) in this theme look like?

- Ensure access to transportation for rural/remote areas for improved youth mobility independence
- Ensure affordable internet access to ensure that all young people, regardless of their background, have equal opportunities to access information.

Implementing Measure no. 1

Title of the implementing measure

- Grant quality internet access to rural areas

Description of the implementing measure

- Expand rural access to internet by introducing physical call towers in rural towns. Giving the possibility for private internet access in the majority of rural houses. This would also allow young people to get access to Wi-Fi on public transportation and in public spaces in rural areas which would grant quality free public access in rural towns.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- Give young people opportunities to socialise, work and learn

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- National

Implementing Measure no. 2

Title of the implementing measure

- Guaranteed on-demand transportation service in rural areas

Description of the implementing measure

- Implement an on-demand transportation service in rural areas, either through government-organized initiatives or facilitated volunteer services. This service would provide flexible, responsive transportation tailored to resident's needs, ensuring better access to essential services, work, and social gatherings. Social volunteers could drive, while the government coordinates the scheduling, funding, raising awareness and oversight of this measure.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- Improved access, reduced isolation, enhanced mobility, community engagement, efficient resources.

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- Regional

Implementing Measure no. 3

Title of the implementing measure

- EU strategy for transportation opportunities in isolated areas

Description of the implementing measure

- Launch of a single EU strategy for interconnecting isolated areas (islands, mountains, overseas etc.) of the Unions. This strategy will incorporate EU funds for transportation infrastructure developed projects, plus a platform where all relevant stakeholders exchange views, expertise, technologies and good practices. The strategy will include a joint universal and updating system and will foremostly involve the Member states and the local communities of the isolated regions.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- Equal access to the opportunities for all EU youth

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- EU level

WG5. Active participation in policy discussions

Guiding question no.1

- There is an intersectional representation, whether formal or informal, direct or indirect, of rural youth in all their diversity in decision-making bodies at all levels, ensuring their meaningful participation.
- There is accountability, trust and eye-level partnership between rural youth and policy and decision makers.

Implementing Measure no. 1

Title of the implementing measure

- **Participatory Budgeting**

Description of the implementing measure

- Implement a **participatory budgeting** process in rural municipalities, allowing rural youth (in all their diversity) to engage in decision making by proposing and voting on budget allocations for local projects/initiatives which are meant to improve different aspects of their lives and are reflective of their needs

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- Greater civic engagement and ensuring that local budgets reflect the needs and interests of rural youth

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- Local

Implementing Measure no. 2

Title of the implementing measure

- Youth Engagement/Outreach

Description of the implementing measure

- Organise **regular meetings** with decision makers in formal/informal settings (parks, mayor's office) and **youth engagement campaigns** by involving existing youth structures including youth organisations to ensure that underrepresented rural youth have access to the decision-making process at local level. Use **mobile youth work** and **detached youth work** to reach out to underrepresented youth with the close partnership of local rural youth (incl. local ambassadors/activists) and youth structures (organisations, informal groups, activists etc.).

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- Ensure underrepresented rural youth are engaged in local policy making dialogue.

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- Local level

Implementing Measure no. 3

Title of the implementing measure

- Systematic Monitoring and Evaluation

Description of the implementing measure

- Establish **systematic mechanisms** to implement, evaluate, and monitor recommendations from rural youth. This will include setting up regular **meetings** between policy makers and representatives from youth structures at local, regional, national, and EU levels. These mechanisms should ensure that youth input is continuously integrated into decision making processes, and progress is evaluated through transparent **monitoring systems** that track the implementation of their recommendations across all levels.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- Greater inclusion and accountability for rural youth in policy making

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- local / regional / national / EU

WG 6. Mental and physical health

What do the desired social change(s) in this theme look like?

- Improved prevention, awareness, and recognition of mental health issues for rural youth, while addressing the risks associated with the digital world.
- Enhanced accessible infrastructure for physical (e.g., parks, gyms) and confidential mental health services (e.g., therapists, community support) tailored to the specific needs of rural youth, along with upgraded public transportation to facilitate access to these services.

Implementing Measure no. 1

Title of the implementing measure

- Empowering ambassadors to campaign and act for rural youth's health.

Description of the implementing measure

- The European Commission and Member States should develop a mental and physical health campaign strategy, which local and regional actors can tailor to their needs. The campaign will support, train and incentivise (potential) ambassadors/multipliers to identify the mental and physical health and related needs of rural youth. Those individuals will raise awareness and lead campaigns, destigmatise mental health issues and bring about positive change in their local communities.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- Empowered ambassadors create awareness, reduce stigma, and inspire local action

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- Eu and national

Implementing Measure no. 2

Title of the implementing measure

- EU and national incentives for mental health educational programmes

Description of the implementing measure

- EU and national governments should provide incentives to ensure that local authorities implement educational programs through workshops for youth to recognise mental health issues and seek help, integrating peer support and interactive activities. Seminars for parents, tailored to local needs, providing guidance on available resources. Teacher training would focus on identifying and supporting students. The programme includes strategies, self-care tools, community involvement, and follow-ups, ensuring long-term impact.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- Destigmatisation

- Create safe place for mental health dialogue
- Cultural adaptation

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- EU & national

Implementing Measure no. 3

Title of the implementing measure

- Creating information structures about funding for rural youth wellbeing facilities

Description of the implementing measure

- European, national, regional and local authorities should improve information structures about the opportunities available to help rural municipalities fund youth centres and initiatives that improve physical and mental health, such as support groups and youth work, making it easier for municipalities to organise services for rural youth.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- Awareness and information about funding
- Improved well-being of rural youth

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- National

WG7. Entrepreneurship, farmership and employment opportunities

What do the desired social change(s) in this theme look like?

- Improving employment conditions in rural areas through developing digital and physical infrastructure, including remote job opportunities, in order to create a better quality of life.
- Redefining the standards of rural living by fostering alternative farming and work pathways in rural areas.

Implementing Measure no. 1

Title of the implementing measure

- Youth Advisory Groups for Rural Entrepreneurship and Employment

Description of the implementing measure

- This measure encourages local municipalities to establish a Youth Advisory Group mechanism focused on entrepreneurship, farmership and employment opportunities for rural youth. These groups shall consist of young individuals selected by their peers. Their primary role is to advise local authorities on initiatives and policies that

support rural youth in starting and sustaining agricultural and entrepreneurial ventures.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- Enhanced rural youth entrepreneurship and employment opportunities, reducing rural depopulation.

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- Local

Implementing Measure no. 2

Title of the implementing measure

- Digital Enhancement of Rural Economic Consolidation through Financial Incentives

Description of the implementing measure

- This measure integrates digital technology (AI, robotics, digital platforms for farming etc.) and machines into farming and rural businesses, automating processes and boosting efficiency. AI-driven tax incentives, microgrants, and regional funding support financial consolidation. Regional authorities will have decision-making power, ensuring that resource allocation and strategies are tailored to the unique needs of each area. A new legal framework facilitates this decentralised approach to enhance local economies and quality of life.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- Higher productivity, economic growth, improved living standards and AI-powered added value optimisation.

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- Regional

Implementing Measure no. 3

Title of the implementing measure

- Providing financial incentives for youth entrepreneurs in rural areas

Description of the implementing measure

- The rural business tax cut program gives businesses lower taxes and grants if they relocate to or start up in rural areas. Companies can pay lower corporate taxes, get discounts on property taxes and earn extra rewards for hiring local people or helping to improve local infrastructure. In return, businesses must agree to stay in the area for at least five years.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- Increase business opportunities in rural areas;

- Attract businesses to rural places.

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- Local/regional

WG8. Climate change and energy scarcity

What do the desired social change(s) in this theme look like?

- Improving climate resilience in rural communities through rural youth representation, enabling sustainable practices and limiting waste of resources
- Ensuring access to safe, clean green sustainably local energy by producing clean green safe energy, while protecting the biodiversity in the process

Implementing Measure no. 1

Title of the implementing measure

- Erasmus + Climate Initiative for Young people in Rural Areas

Description of the implementing measure

- A new initiative within the Erasmus + programme that offers exchanges where young people living in rural areas including young farmers can learn about environmentally sustainable practices e.g. regenerative agriculture and biodiversity conservation. On their return home the participants will deliver a project focused on climate action benefiting their local communities; with the support from a mentor as well as allocated funding. We would encourage the European Commission to consider implementing this initiative within the 2028-2034 Financial Framework.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- Offering mobility for those from rural communities and the opportunity to gain new skills in climate action

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- Offered at EU level as part of the Erasmus + with collaboration from local youth organisations.

Implementing Measure no. 2

Title of the implementing measure

- Ensuring Meaningful Participation of Rural Youth in Climate Policy Making

Description of the implementing measure

- Meaningful participation can be achieved through climate education and awareness-raising initiatives on green skills. Secondly, through capacity-building projects and facilitating access to spaces for rural youth to discuss together their needs and realities on climate change and energy scarcity. Thirdly, rural youth need to be involved in decision-making processes through the setting up of co-management structures like councils including youth seats, advisory committees on climate change and through consultation processes.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- Climate policies reflect the realities of rural communities including youth

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- EU

Implementing Measure no. 3

Title of the implementing measure

- Self-sufficiency in Rural Areas: Sustainable Consumption and Energy Production

Description of the implementing measure

- Funding participatory budgeting to implement more sustainable production and consumption practices, enabling an easier transition to more sustainable modes of producing green energy. Providing incentives, such as tax cuts or subsidies for individuals and local communities seeking to shift to sustainable energy, promoting guidelines on implementing existing resource management practices. Existing policies should be reinforced, such as the ones included in the EU Green Deal, and national policies.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- Strengthening sustainable practices for future generations, autonomy from outside adversarial energy suppliers.

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- Local/regional/national/EU

WG9. Demographic challenges and aging of local communities

What do the desired social change(s) in this theme look like?

- Vibrant and attractive local community with clear vision for the future where the members can help and support each other. There is a strong sense of community with accessible intergenerational dialogue with common spaces.
- The communities can represent themselves in democratic processes.

Implementing Measure no. 1

Title of the implementing measure

- Creation of intergenerational Community Spaces

Description of the implementing measure

- Fund & Support the creation of Community Centres, Parks & Housing. These accessible, diverse and inclusive spaces should be managed by the community through structures which are representative of the entire community in which they are based and democratic in nature. These spaces should foster an atmosphere which is welcoming and accepting and which encourages intergenerational dialogue. Digital spaces could also be explored for this purpose.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- Creating strong community links that support youth alongside others.

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- Local

Implementing Measure no. 2

Title of the implementing measure

- Promote participatory processes

Description of the implementing measure

- Foster youth participation in democracy and within the community. Through initiatives like a future generations commissioner (see Wales), Participatory budgeting, Advisory boards & local Youth Councils and other platforms to give young people political power and include them in democratic structures especially where they may be underrepresented. Ensure communities are involved in decisions about their area e.g. in local planning. Raise awareness about these opportunities in schools & community spaces.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- That rural youth are heard and can shape their future.

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- National

Implementing Measure no. 3

Title of the implementing measure

- Support young people in realising their ideas

Description of the implementing measure

- Reducing barriers to entry for young people starting businesses and implementing ideas. This could include local youth idea funds, Intergenerational mentoring programmes, educating young people on their opportunities, providing funding or tax reductions. This should be administered by youth led structures in the community who will decide on which projects to implement with a focus on small businesses in order to create vibrant rural communities.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- Rural youth is empowered to shape their own community initiatives.

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- Local

WG10. Access to national and EU instruments

What do the desired social change(s) in this theme look like?

- Empowered and confident rural youth. Young people from rural and remote areas are empowered and confident to access and engage with EU and national instruments and initiatives.
- Providing fitting opportunities for rural youth. EU, national and local instruments and initiatives fit the needs and realities as well as capacities and resources of young people from rural and remote areas.

Implementing Measure no. 1

Title of the implementing measure

- Supporting National Agencies in implementing EU programmes for rural youth

Description of the implementing measure

- Rural youth should become one of the priorities of the EU youth programmes, especially the European Solidarity Corps and Erasmus+. The National agencies should be supported to provide assistance in reaching out and informing rural youth, in order to increase their participation. Other EU programmes operating in rural areas should recognise youth engagement as a priority.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- Increased awareness and participation in EU programmes in rural areas.

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- all levels

Implementing Measure no. 2

Title of the implementing measure

- Enhancing Rural Youth Representation in Programme Design through Stakeholder Groups

Description of the implementing measure

- Youth programmes are not well tailored to the interests and needs of the rural youth. We call for the prioritisation of rural youth and a space for discussions on the design of the programmes on a national and European level. On a national level - a stakeholder group, consisting of rural youth representatives and the national agencies, managing relevant programmes; on European – a rural youth representative group to the European Commission.

What key effect(s) will the implementing measure have if it is successful

- more young people from rural areas actively participating in youth programmes

What level is the implementing measure targeted at (local / regional / national / EU):

- National and EU

ANNEX 4: OUTCOMES OF THE WORKING GROUP DELIBERATIONS: FUTURE OF THE EU YOUTH DIALOGUE

WG1: SESSION ON THE FUTURE OF THE EU YOUTH DIALOGUE

Strengths (What makes the EUYD special? What works well in the EUYD?)

- The EU Youth Dialogue serves as the primary consultation tool to gather young people's input for shaping policies.
- It strengthens advocacy for youth organizations.
- It fosters collaboration between young people and decision-makers, ensuring real representation and visibility of youth voices.

Weaknesses (What makes the EUYD weak? What does not work well in EUYD?)

- Ensure diversity in the choice of youth delegates and for youth delegates to be following the process of the whole cycle and ensure participation of high-level participants (e.g. policymakers from the EC).
- Create an institutional memory to avoid repetition in the Dialogue and to help new participants to get to know the role of the Dialogue and history of previous Conferences.
- There is a lack of monitoring and feedback of the outcome of conferences and the dialogue in general.

Opportunities (What opportunities could the EUYD use to become stronger? How can the EUYD better give voice to young people?)

- Focus on current, concrete topics relevant to the EU's ongoing work.
- Establish common standards for all Delegates onboarding and selection processes, ensuring clear roles and duties to optimize expertise and maintain balance.
- Implement EU-wide assessment measures beyond surveys, such as direct dialogues with young people, and develop an impact report to monitor influence. Additionally, ensure regional perspectives are represented by including issues specific to individual countries in supplementary reports.

Threats (What could become problematic for the EUYD in the future? What trends, events, or changes could weaken the EUYD in the future?)

- Democratic backsliding in member countries can affect the level of youth participation. National agendas from the organising countries may delegitimise the process, make our input pointless, or break the continuity of the cycle.
- Constant repetition of topics and recommendations, lack of regular feedback, lack of interest from policymakers, and lack of democratic voting for the recommendations reduce trust towards the dialogue. Lowered trust towards the system makes participants less engaged and participation less meaningful.
- Lower interest and less participation from high-level policymakers make the process less meaningful, and our recommendations not in line with policy limitations, irrelevant to what is decided in the Commission, etc.

WG2: SESSION ON THE FUTURE OF THE EU YOUTH DIALOGUE

Strengths (What makes the EUYD special? What works well in the EUYD?)

- It is a great opportunity to speak with decision-makers about topics which are relevant for young people, allowing the same youths to also participate, and share their voices and thoughts about the EU and what can be improved.
- It is an opportunity to find out how youngsters feel and what they think about European goals and get recommendations on how to achieve them from all the different participating delegates, NGOs, and ministries.
- You meet a number of people with different perspectives, coming from different backgrounds, which gives one insight as to whether certain policies work, and why some others don't, even though the help of the facilitators input.

Weaknesses (What makes the EUYD weak? What does not work well in EUYD?)

- Lack of diversity in the participants: under representation of marginalized groups.
- Lack of information, visibility and communication about the EUYD.
- Inadequate working agenda and methodology.

Opportunities (What opportunities could the EUYD use to become stronger? How can the EUYD better give voice to young people?)

- Participants should be provided with relevant EU resources in advance to prepare for their Working Group topics.
- Establishing a mechanism to monitor the implementation of ideas proposed during the European Youth Conference (EYC).
- Encouraging delegates to gather feedback from national stakeholders on the EYC topic to ensure inclusive perspective.

Threats (What could become problematic for the EUYD in the future? What trends, events, or changes could weaken the EUYD in the future?)

- Recommendations could be ignored by the policy-makers, the process will lose credibility and participants.
- Political trends could lead to a cut in funding, thus, abolishing the youth conference. .
- Organising countries can manipulate results by changing the topic midway through the implementation process.

WG3: SESSION ON THE FUTURE OF THE EU YOUTH DIALOGUE

Strengths (What makes the EUYD special? What works well in the EUYD?)

- Involvement of young people and decision makers in the EU Dialogue
- Connecting and strengthening the connection between EU institutions and young people from EU countries and beyond (non-EU countries)

Weaknesses (What makes the EUYD weak? What does not work well in EUYD?)

- Promotion of the process and its outcomes as well as lack of information and visibility to external young people
- Inclusion and lack of involvement of young people from all backgrounds
- Continuity between the cycles and conference

Opportunities (What opportunities could the EUYD use to become stronger? How can the EUYD better give voice to young people?)

- Involving in EUYD youth delegates from EU candidates countries to EU membership (Moldova, Ukraine, etc) and INGYO delegates

- Share and co-work on youth priorities together and to voice youth perspectives
- One problem from the different shape of view, depending on background to shape youth policies: no decisions without youth

Threats (What could become problematic for the EUYD in the future? What trends, events, or changes could weaken the EUYD in the future?)

- Recommendations are vague and not implemented
- Lower representation of youth NGOs

WG4: SESSION ON THE FUTURE OF THE EU YOUTH DIALOGUE

Strengths (What makes the EUYD special? What works well in the EUYD?)

- Diversity and richness of perspectives and intercultural experiences of participants/organizations
- Creates opportunities for connection and networking
- Creates opportunities to express opinion towards needed change

Weaknesses (What makes the EUYD weak? What does not work well in EUYD?)

- Lack of transparency and follow up: in Implementation (Lack of inclusion of different ministries within EUYD) and on Process inside EU institutions (Not clear what happens with documents inside EU institutions)
- Lack of visibility of the entire EUYD on all levels
- Preparatory communication needs to be clearer

Opportunities (What opportunities could the EUYD use to become stronger? How can the EUYD better give voice to young people?)

- More consistent (EU) decision-makers and (EU) expertise throughout the whole process
- Establish preparatory documents for participants in enough time to prepare for the conference
- Creating space for commenting on on-going EU work/policies

Threats (What could become problematic for the EUYD in the future? What trends, events, or changes could weaken the EUYD in the future?)

- Lack of unity within the presidency which transfers to the fact that cycles don't align
- Youth washing. Non-realistic recommendations create a false view of youth
- Doing nothing to improve EUYD which would result of EUYD ineffectiveness.

WG5: SESSION ON THE FUTURE OF THE EU YOUTH DIALOGUE

Strengths (What makes the EUYD special? What works well in the EUYD?)

- Engages a broad range of young people in policy discussions
- Formally established platform for youth participation in decision making processes and a means to influence EU policies
- A good practice to be replicated in the non-EU countries

Weaknesses (What makes the EUYD weak? What does not work well in EUYD?)

- Lack of follow up and monitoring system/mechanisms of the EUYD process and outcomes
- Underutilisation of available funds within the EUYD by some of the member states and not enough funding for INGYOs

- Lack of communication and enough visibility of the EUDY for inclusion of unorganised and underrepresented youth (outside of usual bubble)

Opportunities (What opportunities could the EUYD use to become stronger? How can the EUYD better give voice to young people?)

- Learning from best practices from other member states and creating synergies with other EU programmes
- Commitments of the EC to strengthen the EUYD (right momentum)
- Available. reports, data and recommendation of the effectiveness of the EUYD

Threats (What could become problematic for the EUYD in the future? What trends, events, or changes could weaken the EUYD in the future?)

- Changes in political leadership or priorities in member states potentially impacting the continuity and/or effectiveness of the dialogue, tokenistic participation
- Growing disengagement and lack of trust among young people causing reduce participation and the impact of the dialogue
- Other similar programmes which can shade the light of the EUYD (competition instead of cooperation)

WG6: SESSION ON THE FUTURE OF THE EU YOUTH DIALOGUE

Strengths (What makes the EUYD special? What works well in the EUYD?)

- Engaged and Enthusiastic Participants: The event attracts driven, energetic, and inspired individuals, creating a great atmosphere for active participation.
- Networking and Collaboration: It offers valuable opportunities to build connections, share best practices, exchange knowledge, and foster collaboration among participants.
- Concrete Outcomes and Learning Opportunities: The well-thought-out process leads to tangible results that can be implemented for positive impact. Participants, gain new insights, experiences, and knowledge about European and local opportunities.

Weaknesses (What makes the EUYD weak? What does not work well in EUYD?)

- Limited representation and inclusion: The EUYD participants often come from homogeneous backgrounds, lacking diversity in social, economic, and geographic representation, leading to insufficient inclusivity.
- Lack of clear communication and continuity: There is inadequate communication between conferences, and with participants, making it difficult for attendees and the general public to see how each step connects and be aware of the opportunities the EUYD presents. There's also insufficient continuity between cycles, hindering progress.
- Ineffective follow-ups and local implementation: The follow-up with participants and local communities can be improved, with more guidance on how to implement ideas at the national or local level, hence limiting the tangible impact of the discussions.

Opportunities (What opportunities could the EUYD use to become stronger? How can the EUYD better give voice to young people?)

- Strong support for the EUYD from various stakeholders, including the European Commission, youth delegates, and national authorities.
- Valuable input from young people: Maximize this by strengthening the connection between policymakers and delegates.
- The EUYD serves as a good practice model for other countries and can contribute to capacity building efforts.

Threats (What could become problematic for the EUYD in the future? What trends, events, or changes could weaken the EUYD in the future?)

- Loss of trust in processes and institutions due to a lack of transparency, impact, and effectiveness.
- Austerity policies affecting the process.
- Undemocratic policies hinder meaningful youth participation through various practices.

WG7: SESSION ON THE FUTURE OF THE EU YOUTH DIALOGUE

Strengths (What makes the EUYD special? What works well in the EUYD?)

- A youth-led inclusive process which gives the opportunity to all young people to participate and express their diverse views, feeling in this way better engaged in the decision making process and closer to the EU.
- Fostering democratic dialogue and bringing stakeholders close in large numbers.
- Strong institutional support.

Weaknesses (What makes the EUYD weak? What does not work well in EUYD?)

- The implementing measures as a part of the activity of EUYCs and EUYD lack the necessary legal force in order to be implemented on national, regional or local level.
- The proposals and recommendations made at the EUYC and during the EUYD may be altered or ignored without consequences.
- Lack of diversity in the European Union's dialogue with young people could be the limited inclusion of diverse perspectives and voices from various socio-economic, cultural and regional backgrounds.

Opportunities (What opportunities could the EUYD use to become stronger? How can the EUYD better give voice to young people?)

- Connecting diverse communities: Promote trust-building between decision-makers and youth from various backgrounds and countries, encouraging understanding and reaching young people with diverse profiles.
- Increased EU funding: Access more EU funds for dialogue, participation projects, and youth involvement on national level, expanding outreach of EU values.
- Youth-driven policy influence: Empower young people to contribute with new ideas and make a real impact on policy decisions, focusing on serious and urgent issues.

Threats (What could become problematic for the EUYD in the future? What trends, events, or changes could weaken the EUYD in the future?)

- Shift in political priorities or change/radicalisation of mindsets that may lead to a disruption or suspension of the EUYD.
- Inequality of access in the process, resulting in certain voices not heard and certain more privileged groups overrepresented.
- Lack of interest in the recommendations or ignoring them completely.

WG8: SESSION ON THE FUTURE OF THE EU YOUTH DIALOGUE

Strengths (What makes the EUYD special? What works well in the EUYD?)

- Participation. The European Youth Dialogue is the biggest youth participation instrument in the world, involving the different perspectives of young people across Europe, including EU candidate countries and neighbouring countries.

- Well-balanced representation process. It enables structured dialogue between youth delegates, ministerial delegates, the INGYOs, and the European Commission, each participating side bringing in their own thematic knowledge and expertise.
- Structured framework. The 18 month cycle allows for enough time to discuss issues and prioritise solutions, supported by a sustainable grant mechanism at Commission level. This guarantees that the European Youth Dialogue can have a strong impact on policy and decision making at all levels.

Weaknesses (What makes the EUYD weak? What does not work well in EUYD?)

- Governance of Participation At the moment participation involves the same young people at every EUYD, therefore, different faces should be involved as well as the added participation of youth ministers, the Commissioner and all of the EU institutions. EUYD delegates are not well-prepared from beforehand and there needs to be a greening approach to the organisation of the event through sustainable means
- Communication & Dissemination Lack of dissemination of information and impact assessments of the EUYD on a national and international level.
- Follow up Lack of clear follow up on the respective levels and competences (EU, national, regional) and the need for transparency on what happened with the demands/recommendations on all levels (ex post analysis). Secure long-term funding for follow up and for candidate countries and YNGOs

Opportunities (What opportunities could the EUYD use to become stronger? How can the EUYD better give voice to young people?)

- Increasing Inclusivity There is an opportunity to make the EUYD more inclusive by actively involving EU candidate countries and relevant member organizations in the process. Expanding participation would ensure a broader representation of diverse perspectives, enriching the dialogue and making it more reflective of the wider European context.
- Enhancing the Impact of Working Group Discussions The effectiveness of Working Group discussions could be significantly improved by allocating more space to explore national consultations, specific goals, and relevant political agendas. By focusing more on these areas, WG discussions can lead to more concrete outcomes that resonate with young people's priorities at the national level and drive meaningful change.
- Aligning EUYD Topics with EU Policy Agendas Greater alignment between the EUYD's thematic focus and ongoing discussions within the EU would increase the relevance and impact of the dialogue. By connecting the topics discussed in the EUYD to current EU policy decisions and debates, the process can better influence the political agenda and ensure that young people's voices are directly contributing to shaping EU policies.

Threats (What could become problematic for the EUYD in the future? What trends, events, or changes could weaken the EUYD in the future?)

- Lack of political will to protecting the independence, safety and freedom of expression of youth organizations and delegates, and to commit to democratic values.
- Lack of accountability in regards to the outcomes of EUYC from the EU and members states leading to disengagement and/or reducing levels of engagement of young people
- Insufficient funding threatening the participation of wide range of young people - IYNGOs, representatives of neighboring and candidate countries damaging the quality of discussions and outcomes.

WG9: SESSION ON THE FUTURE OF THE EU YOUTH DIALOGUE

Strengths (What makes the EUYD special? What works well in the EUYD?)

- Existence of EUYD means an existence of space for people from around the EU to discuss youth policies. It can also unite the countries.
- Youth have real life experience of creating policies thanks to the EUYD. For some it is the very first time (for some even the only time) when they can be creating policies.
- EUYD is essential to raise awareness of the needs of young people.

Weaknesses (What makes the EUYD weak? What does not work well in EUYD?)

- There is a low visibility of the result and the dialogue over all. Most of the youth don't know about the existence of EUYD (in contrast to Erasmus+ for example).
- There is no book on how to implement the EUYD recommendations. The implementation results are different all over the EU.
- There is a lack of follow up and of monitoring the implementation of recommendation.

Opportunities (What opportunities could the EUYD use to become stronger? How can the EUYD better give voice to young people?)

- EUYD should involve more young people with disabilities, fewer opportunities as well as people from underrepresented regions (with inclusion of non-EU regions) into the EUYD dialogue and the dissemination process of EUYD.
- Representation should be stronger. That means better preparation of delegates, clearer mandate for delegates etc.
- The EUYD process, results and the involvement of other stakeholders should all be operating on a higher political level, influence and prestige.

Threats (What could become problematic for the EUYD in the future? What trends, events, or changes could weaken the EUYD in the future?)

- Youth can lose trust and interest in the EUYD, politics, policy makers, government etc. The same applies the other way → the countries can become more national oriented and lose interest in the EU processes.
- The question of funding vs. impact in the long run.
- The EUYD processes can become less and less youth-led.

WG10: SESSION ON THE FUTURE OF THE EU YOUTH DIALOGUE

Strengths (What makes the EUYD special? What works well in the EUYD?)

- Youth participation and involvement in dialogue with institutions, stakeholders, INYGOS on different levels
- Creating a community for young people making their voice heard with bottom-up process
- EUYD offers a platform for exchange of good practices and different youth perspectives in the decision making process

Weaknesses (What makes the EUYD weak? What does not work well in EUYD?)

- Lack of continuity and conformity across the conferences within and throughout the cycle (each conference should serve a role, lack of clear communication of methodology in advance, difference in age range and number of youth delegates)
- Lack of inclusivity throughout the phases of the dialogue and lack of expertise on the topic of discussions (a trend of decreasing number of INYGOS, non-EU countries do not receive financial support)

- Difficulty of implementing the recommendations and measures in the given time frames and lack of accountability

Opportunities (What opportunities could the EUYD use to become stronger? How can the EUYD better give voice to young people?)

- Create an effective communication channel between youth and decision-makers and mainstream the impact of the dialogue.
- Expanding partnerships with relevant stakeholders such as COE (as well as other youth initiatives) and mapping out ways to maximise the use of INGYO expertise in the EU Youth conf.
- Promoting European values outside of the EU by including YDS of the COE countries.

Threats (What could become problematic for the EUYD in the future? What trends, events, or changes could weaken the EUYD in the future?)

- Political evolution could make the EU Youth dialogue process and results marginalised
- Risk of distrusting the process if the representativity is not inclusive enough
- Distrusting the process for lack of follow up or feedback on the results

ANNEX 4: POLICYMAKERS SUPPORTING WORKING GROUPS

- **WG1:** Viktor Zoltán MARUZSA, State Secretary for Public Education, Ministry of the Interior (Hungary)
- **WG2:** Szilvia BALOGH, Deputy State Secretary for Employment and Adult Education at the Ministry of Technology and Industry, Ministry of Technology and Industry (Hungary)
- **WG3:** Balázs MOLNÁR, Deputy State Secretary responsible for European policy, Ministry for European Affairs (Hungary)
- **WG4:** András KISS, Head of Department, KTM (Hungary)
- **WG5:** Zsófia NAGY-VARGHA, Deputy State Secretary responsible for youth, Ministry of Culture and Innovation (Hungary)
- **WG5:** Gábor CSABA, Deputy Secretary responsible for cultural diplomacy, , Ministry of Culture and Innovation (Hungary)
- **WG6:** Judit BIDLÓ, Deputy State Secretary for the Professional Management of Healthcare, Ministry of the Interior (Hungary)
- **WG7:** Anikó JUHÁSZ, Deputy State Secretary for Agriculture, Ministry of Agriculture (Hungary)
- **WG8:** Daniella DELI, Deputy State Secretary responsible for climate policy, Ministry of Energy (Hungary)
- **WG9:** Attila BENEDA, Deputy State Secretary for family affairs, Ministry of Culture and Innovation (Hungary)
- **WG10:** Biliana SIRAKOVA, EU Youth Co-ordinator, European Commission
- **WG10:** Richárd BODROGI, Director General, Tempus Közalapítvány (Hungary)